

Webhooks and Webhook endpoints

Version: 0.1

Status: DRAFT

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The ARIA platform can send webhook pings to an endpoint based on certain criteria. Endpoints can be registered for events and “contexts”, to which a payload is delivered.

A webhook listener can be registered to send matching events and / or matching contents of a context to a given endpoint. ARIA will attempt to match incoming events and contexts via registered regex, and dispatch them accordingly.

Registering an endpoint

If you are a site administrator, it is possible to register a webhook endpoint over the API. Alternatively, one can be set up by the ARIA team.

The ability to add hooks will likely be expanded for other classes of users, but at time of writing, this is the current situation.

To do this, use the following mutation:

```
addHookSubscriber(input: {  
  site_id: "0d6d75a6-bce5-4015-a639-d2c6bf00c473",  
  label: "This is my example Hook",  
  url: "https://example.com/ping/",  
  hook: "/example.event.[a-zA-Z0-9]+/",  
  context: {  
    an_expected_key: "/regex[0..9]+/"  
  }  
}) {  
  id  
}
```

Name	Type	Comment
site_id	UUID	The UUID of
label	String	Arbitrary descriptive label
url	URL	The url of the endpoint
hook	String	The event, e.g. “visit.created”, may also be regex
context	JSON Object	JSON Blob describing the context dispatched with the event. This is a collection of key => value pairs, where the value can be a set value or a regex string.

Anatomy of a Ping

The anatomy of a webhook is as follows:

Name	Type	Comment
version	String ("1.0")	Version of webhook. Currently this will be 1.0, but will allow us to extend and change the format in future
event	String	The event, e.g. "visit.created"
context	JSON Object	JSON Blob describing the context dispatched with the event.
payload	JSON Object	JSON Blob containing the event specific payload

Context is a key => value pair on to which value will be matched via regex. Event is a string, e.g. visit.created, which can be matched by your handler on regex.

When you receive this ping you should unpack and handle accordingly.

Generally, in ARIA, a ping will be "thin", containing only minimal information (e.g. a visit ID in the case of visit.created/visit.updated). The intention is that you should use the corresponding API query to pull the full record.

This is done deliberately to ensure that any confidential data is only disclosed to authorised users.

Handling the ping

How your application processes this ping is up to you, however regardless, you should tell ARIA how you choose to handle it using HTTP status codes.

Status Code	Meaning
200	Processed successfully
4xx	Processed with error, ARIA will not attempt delivery
5xx	Unhandled, ARIA will attempt redelivery for a predefined number of times before aborting.

Version History

Version	Description
0.1	Initial draft